

Universidad Pública de Navarra
Nafarroako Unibertsitate Publikoa

**ESCUELA TÉCNICA SUPERIOR DE INGENIERÍA AGRÓNOMICA Y
BIOCIENCIAS**

**NEKAZARITZAKO INGENIARITZAKO ETA BIOZIENTZIETAKO GOI
MAILAKO ESKOLA TEKNIKOA**

Machine Learning Techniques for Enhance Amplitude Patterns from
Phased-arrays Augmented with an Holographic Plate

presentado por

Mikel Aldea Esnaola

aurkeztua

**GRADO EN CIENCIA DE DATOS
GRADUA DATUEN ZIENTZIETAN**

Septiembre, 2023 / 2023, Iraila

Abstract

Phased-arrays are an array of transducers, in which the relative amplitudes and phases of each emitter are controllably varied in order to design the acoustic pressure pattern emitted by the array. The control of these transducers enables to generate a desired amplitude pattern at a certain distance. The quality of these patterns can be enhanced by adding an holographic plate modulator at an intermediate distance between the emitters and the target. Here, we propose new techniques using a Neural Network architecture to compute the parameters of the phased-array and the holographic plate needed to generate the desired pattern.

Key Words

Acoustic holograms, Ultrasound, Holographic techniques, Deep Learning, Neural Networks, Auto-Encoder

Resumen

Las antenas en fase son un conjunto de transductores en los que las amplitudes y las fases de cada emisor se varían controladamente para alterar el patrón de presión acústica diseñado por los transductores. El control de estos transductores permite generar un patrón de amplitud deseado a una distancia determinada. La calidad de estos patrones se puede mejorar agregando una placa holográfica a una distancia intermedia entre los emisores y el objetivo. Aquí, se proponen nuevas técnicas que utilizan una arquitectura de red neuronal para calcular los parámetros de las antenas en fase y la placa holográfica necesarios para generar el patrón deseado.

Palabras Clave

Hologramas acústicos, Ultrasonido, Técnicas Holográficas, Aprendizaje Profundo, Redes Neuronales, Auto-Encoder

Agradecimientos

En primer lugar, quiero agradecer a mi director de TFG Asier Marzo Pérez por todo el apoyo, ayuda e implicación mostrada durante estos meses de trabajo. Gracias a él he podido aprender mucho acerca de acústica, la cual era un tema que no dominaba en un principio y gracias a su apoyo me ha ayudado a intentar aportar, aunque sea un granito de arena al tema.

También me gustaría agradecer a todo el equipo de UpnaLab, en especial a Manuel López-Amo Ocón y a Jon Goikoetxea por su colaboración y ayuda en el proyecto. Gracias a todos me he sentido muy bien acogido en su equipo y contagiado por sus ganas de aprender y de adquirir conocimiento.

Por último, me gustaría agradecer a mis padres Javier Aldea Subiran y Mari Mar Esnaola Bermejo, a mi hermano Asier Aldea Esnaola y a toda mi familia y amigos, por todo el apoyo mostrado a lo largo de mi vida. De todo corazón, muchas gracias.

Contents

1	Introduction	4
2	State of Art	4
3	Experiments	6
3.1	Modeling of the Problem	6
3.2	Forward Step of the Physical Part of the Neural Network	8
3.3	Architectures Propose for the Virtual Part	11
3.3.1	Diffracted Acoustic Network	11
3.3.2	One-Hot Layer Model	12
3.3.3	Encoder Decoder Diffractive Network	14
3.4	Simulation Set Up	15
4	Results	18
4.1	Pure Array Optimization	18
4.2	Diffracted Acoustic Network	20
4.3	One-Hot Layer Model	20
4.4	Encoder Decoder Diffractive Network	21
4.5	Comparison of all models	21
5	Conclusions and Future Work	25
6	References	26
7	Supplemental Information	27

1 Introduction

Holographic techniques has diverse applications, such as in fields like medicine [1], biology [2] and engineering [3]. All, this sort of applications include different aspects such as volumetric displays [4] or particle manipulation [5]. In all of these applications, acoustic holograms must generate an acoustic pressure control pattern at a specified position. There multiple ways to generate an acoustic field, here we are use phased array transducers (PATs). A PATs is composed of many elements arranged that emit acoustic energy at different times in order to direct the sound wave in a specific direction. The amplitudes and phases needed to create that pattern can be computed with pure array optimization, but recently some deep learning techniques has been used to achieve this goal.

Usually, with a high number of transducer a good resolution pattern can be achieved, but this is generally expensive. In order, to try to reduce this amount, new techniques that incorporate the use of holographic plates have recently been gaining popularity.

2 State of Art

In terms of generating acoustic patterns, many methods involving the used of phased array have been proposed.

Some remarkable methods use pure phased array optimization via iteration methods like proposed by Weibai Li et al. [6] on November 2022, where they used this iterative method to compute an optimized phase distribution for generating different figures such as an “S” or a kangaroo shape pattern.

Another methods use automatic differentiation such as the one proposed by Fushimi et al [7] in June 2021. Fushimi et al. proposed a phase-only gradient-descent algorithm with automatic differentiation as a new platform for optimizing acoustic holograms. On their paper, they use a large variety of phased array like 14x14 or 32x32, adding flexibility to the problem and achieving better results that the previous works.

Other methods involve the use of deep learning techniques such as Neural Network like the method proposed by Boyi Li et al. [8] in June 2022 where they come up with the design of an unsupervised Neural Network base on a U-Net architecture where they combined the use of CNN’s and Transformers to learn the local and the global features of the acoustic hologram. Similarly, Lin et al. [9] on July 2023 design a physics-enhanced deep neural network also base on a U-Net for generating multi-frequency acoustic holograms.

All of these techniques are based on the use of phased arrays, which means that in order to achieve a good quality acoustic pressure pattern, these phased arrays need to have a sufficient number of transducers to achieve it. This means that many transducers are needed (on the order of 256 or 512 or up to 1024), which are expensive. In order, to try to reduce this amount, new techniques that incorporate the use of holographic plates have recently been

gaining popularity.

The first appearance of the use of an holographic plate was proposed by Melde et al. in this paper [10] on 2016. On this paper they create a ripple on the surface of the water by using ultrasonic waves emanating from a speaker underneath. But crucially, the waves coming from the speaker pass through a hologram plate. On this holographic plate some parts are thicker than others. Where it's thicker, the waves take longer to pass through and this creates a distortion pattern. As the waves reach the surface, they form the shape of the ripple. Using this technique, researchers can create all kinds of patterns, like a dove, this patterns will have much more resolution and accuracy than without using the holographic plate.

The milestone of this paper was that they were able to generate an acoustic pattern with an incredible resolutions just by using one transducer and an hologram plate. The limitations were that the holographic plate modifies the wavefront of just a single ultrasonic transducer, which means that, for each pattern they want to do, they need to built a new holographic plate designed specifically to make that and only that pattern.

Then on May 2023, Athanassiadis et al. [11] proposed a new method called Multiplane Diffractive Acoustic Networks (DAN) in which they were able to apply this technique to more than one transducer and thus they create more than one pattern using the same holographic plate. Of course, this holographic plate performs worse on a pattern than a plate specifically created for that pattern, but it was a huge milestone because it was the first time that an holographic plate was used to generate more than a single pattern. In order to achieve this, they transform the problem into a neural network including the holographic plate as customized layer of the model.

The limitation of this method has to do with the way in which they modeled the inputs necessary to train the neural network. What they did was use the phased array itself as input, when the phased array transducers must be trained to know what to emit in order to obtain one pattern or another. This then leads to the question of what should the input be in order to generate a desired pattern (that is, what does the transducers in the phased array have to emit). So, in this way, the inputs also need to be trained along with the rest of the parameters of the neural network. But generally in a neural network the input are fixed and are not trained, which is why with that architecture that they proposed they were not able to train the part of the phased array. To solve this problem they decided to assign each emitter to each pattern, so they pass as input a one-hot vector (a vector of all zeros except a one) in which the one corresponded to the emitter on the phased array that was turned on to recreate that pattern and the rest emitters remained off. In this way they already knew the inputs to train the neural network. The limitation that this entails is that if you have N emitters you can only generate N patterns. They later tested configurations of pairs of emitters turned on at the same time being able of generate $\binom{N}{2} = \frac{N \cdot (N-1)}{2}$ patterns, but the results were experimentally worse than when they turned on a single emitters and they still have some amount of emitters that where not contributing in generating certain patterns.

Here, we propose different neural network architectures that are able to use all the transducer at the same time for generating all patterns, solving the issue of only just being able to use a single emitter for each pattern.

3 Experiments

3.1 Modeling of the Problem

To compute the amplitude and phase of the phased array and the phase shift of the holographic plate needed to achieve the desired patterns we are going to use artificial intelligence techniques, precisely neural networks, but as the problem is based on a physical problem, the neural network must be subject it to some constraints in order to modulate how the real world works.

A conventional neural network (as shown in Fig.1) is made of layers, in the figure there is one input layer, one hidden layer and one output layer, in reality there can be more than one hidden layer. Each layer can have an arbitrary amount of nodes. In Fig. 1 each layer has n nodes, but it doesn't necessarily have to be like that.

Figure 1: A Conventional Neural Network with one hidden layer

In a dense neural network (as shown in the figure) or also called fully connected neural networks, all nodes in the previous layer (N nodes) are connected to all the nodes in the next layer (M nodes) by a weight w_{nm} , also for each node m there is a bias b_m . Both parameters need to be training. For each individual node j a predicted value h_j is computing by using the formula bellow:

$$h_j = f \left(b_j + \sum_{i=1}^n w_i \cdot x_i \right) \quad \forall j \in [1, m] \tag{1}$$

However, for our problem we need to make some changes in the architecture and the parameters that need to be trained, because we are subject to suit the real life problem. What we

want to do is to model the problem in such a way that it resembles the real problem as closely as possible. For that, our input layer will represent our phased array, composed by $N \times N$ transducers, the hidden layer will be the holographic plate, formed by $M \times M$ pixels and the output layer will be the chosen height at which the patterns will be constructed (discretized into $S \times S$ control points). A 3D representation of the model is shown at Fig. 2.

Figure 2: 3D Representation of the problem

But the transformation of the problem into a neural network is tricky because here the input (which will be what should the emitters emit in order to create a specific pattern) needs to be **trained**, and usually in a neural network does not the case. But also, here the weights will represent the propagation of the acoustic wave from each emitter in the phased array to each pixel of the holographic plate, so they are **fixed** and they will **not be trained**. What will indeed be trained, is going to be the phase shift that each pixel on the holographic plate will applied to the wave that reaches that point. Furthermore, as we are working with waves we will work with complex numbers.

So in summary, each emitter in the phased array is going to have two parameters, the amplitude and the phase of the wave it creates, this parameters will be trained. Then all the created waves will travel from the phased array to the height at which the holographic plate is located, this will represent the weights w_1 in a conventional neural network but with the particularity that this weights will not be trained and will be compute using physics laws. We will also have no activation function. So, with this computation we will know the acoustic pressure that reaches the holographic plate. An holographic plate is made up of many holes ($M \times M$), of different widths and depending on the width each hole has, a different phase shift will be applied to the wave, our task will also be to compute which phase shift should each hole have to redirected the wave and create the desire patterns, this could be consider similar to a conventional bias b , because it is individual for each node. Then at the end, following the

law of physics, we will compute the propagation of the wave to the height where we want to produces the desired patterns, this will be analogous to w_2 in a conventional NN. The amplitude of the acoustic pressure produced at that height will be our pattern. A representation of the problem model as a neural network can be seen at Fig. 3.

Figure 3: Neural Network Architecture propose to model the problem

The propagators (denoted as T_1 and T_2 in Fig. 3) to determine the acoustic pressure that a transducer n produces at a point m are usually called transfer matrices. To compute this transfer matrices we will use the matrix method for acoustic levitation proposed in this paper [12] which is equivalent to the Rayleigh integral. So the transfer matrices can be computed as:

$$T_{mn} = s_n \frac{e^{ikr_{nm}}}{r_{nm}} \quad (2)$$

Where $i = \sqrt{-1}$ and $k = \frac{\omega}{c}$ is the wavenumber, usually called repetency and is the spatial frequency of a wave, it is made up of the angular frequency $\omega = 2\pi f$ and in our case $f = 40000Hz$, c is the velocity of the sound in the medium, in our case air, $c = 340(m/s)$ and r_{nm} is the distance between the transducer n and the point in space m .

3.2 Forward Step of the Physical Part of the Neural Network

Once all the elements in the physical model of the neural network have been explained, then it is timed to explain how the forward step is done. As we are using TensorFlow library [13] it is only needed to define the forward step of the NN and the software itself of TensorFlow will take care of the backward step.

So, first of all, we are going to initialize randomly the amplitudes and phases of the Phased Array. Amplitudes (A) will be initialized with values between 0 and 1 and phases (θ) will be initialized with values between $-\pi$ and π . With these two values we will be able to create the complex number that will represent the acoustic wave created for each transducer, that is to

say: $A_j e^{i\theta_j} \quad \forall j \in [1, N^2]$.

After that, we will compute the acoustic pressure $P = [p_1, p_2, \dots, p_{M^2}]^T$ that reaches each pixel of the holographic plate, for that, we will use the matrix method [12]:

$$\begin{pmatrix} p_1 \\ p_2 \\ \vdots \\ p_{M^2} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} T_{11} & T_{12} & \dots & T_{1N^2} \\ T_{21} & T_{22} & \dots & T_{2N^2} \\ \vdots & & \ddots & \\ T_{M^2 1} & T_{M^2 2} & \dots & T_{M^2 N^2} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} A_1 e^{i\theta_1} \\ A_2 e^{i\theta_2} \\ \vdots \\ A_{N^2} e^{i\theta_{N^2}} \end{pmatrix} \quad (3)$$

$(M^2, 1) \qquad (M^2 \times N^2) \qquad (N^2, 1)$

This is equivalent in a Neural Network when we multiply the inputs and the weights, but in this case the "weights" (T_{nm}) are not trainable and we are working with complex numbers instead of real numbers.

Then once the wave reaches the holographic plate, a phase shift in the wave occurs. The hologram converts a planar wavefront from the transducer into the required phase distribution. This travelling wave diffracts to form an image in the target plane. This means that, after the wave reaches the holographic plate it passes through holes of different widths, in those holes the phase of the wave is redirected in order to guide the wave to create patterns. An example of how this works can be seen in Fig. 4.

Figure 4: Example of how an holographic plate redirects the wavefront. Image extracted from Holograms for Acoustics (September 2016) [10]

This phase shift mathematically can be applied by multiplying the acoustic pressure by a complex number of amplitude 1 and a phase that is the desired phase shift $\Delta\theta$. As for each pixels in the holographic plate there is an specific phase shift I will denote each phase shift with a subscript j , so $\Delta_j\theta_j \quad \forall j \in [1, M^2]$.

So for each point in the holographic plate when the acoustic pressure $p_j = A_j e^{i\theta_j}$ reaches, it is multiply by this complex numbers what causes:

$$p_j \cdot e^{i\Delta_j\theta_j} = A_j e^{i\theta_j} \cdot e^{i\Delta_j\theta_j} = A_j e^{i(\theta_j + \Delta_j\theta_j)} = A_j e^{i\theta_j(1 + \Delta_j)} \quad (4)$$

A representation of how this phase shift looks in the complex space can be seen at Fig. 5.

Figure 5: Representation of a phase shift in the complex space

So what happens after the wave passes through the holographic plate is that the acoustic pressure that is coming out of the wave will be modified as it follows:

$$\begin{pmatrix} p_1 \\ p_2 \\ \vdots \\ p_{M^2} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} A_1 e^{i\theta_1} \\ A_2 e^{i\theta_2} \\ \vdots \\ A_{M^2} e^{i\theta_{M^2}} \end{pmatrix} \rightarrow \begin{pmatrix} A_1 e^{i\theta_1(1 + \Delta_1)} \\ A_2 e^{i\theta_2(1 + \Delta_2)} \\ \vdots \\ A_{M^2} e^{i\theta_{M^2}(1 + \Delta_{M^2})} \end{pmatrix} \quad (5)$$

Then, again, using the transfer matrix method we carry the resultant wave to the target distance computing the final acoustic pressure $[p_1^F, p_2^F, \dots, p_{S^2}^F]^T$, that reaches the target plane (which is discretized into $(S \times S)$ control points:

$$\begin{pmatrix} p_1^F \\ p_2^F \\ \vdots \\ p_{S^2}^F \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} T_{11} & T_{12} & \dots & T_{1M^2} \\ T_{21} & T_{22} & \dots & T_{2M^2} \\ \vdots & & \ddots & \\ T_{S^2 1} & T_{S^2 2} & \dots & T_{S^2 M^2} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} A_1 e^{i\theta_1(1 + \Delta_1)} \\ A_2 e^{i\theta_2(1 + \Delta_2)} \\ \vdots \\ A_{M^2} e^{i\theta_{M^2}(1 + \Delta_{M^2})} \end{pmatrix} \quad (6)$$

$(S^2, 1) \qquad (S^2 \times M^2) \qquad (M^2, 1)$

As a final step, we will compute the amplitude value of the acoustic pressure that reaches the target distance, this amplitude will be what will define the pattern. For that, in the end of the output layer we will apply a transformation using the function f , which will consist of

transforming the resultants complex numbers into real numbers just taking into account the amplitude of the complex numbers. Depending on whether the complex number is expressed in its exponential form or in its Cartesian form the function f will be:

$$\begin{aligned}
 f : \mathbb{C} &\rightarrow \mathbb{R} \\
 z = Ae^{i\theta} &\rightarrow f(z) = A \quad (\text{Exponential Form}) \\
 z = a + bi &\rightarrow f(z) = \sqrt{a^2 + b^2} \quad (\text{Cartesian Form})
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{7}$$

Finally a reshape is done to convert the $[S^2, 1]$ vector into an image of $[S \times S]$ pixels. Obtaining the final patterns.

3.3 Architectures Propose for the Virtual Part

Here, we are going to propose different techniques that can be used to train the model. As it has been explained above, on this problem the inputs of the physical part need to be trained so some sort type of architectures needs to be add before the input layer in order to make it trainable by the neural network. Here we are going to propose different ways in which we can approach this problem.

3.3.1 Diffracted Acoustic Network

The Diffracted Acoustic Network (DAN), as explained in the state of the art, was proposed by Athanassiadis et al. in may 2023 [11]. In this method, they used a multi-layer hologram that can project multiple pressure fields with higher quality than a single-plane hologram. It is a huge milestone because they created the first projector that allows to projects more fields that input transducers.

In order to solving the issue of having to train the emitters they used as input a one-hot vector (a vector of all zeros except a one), so for instance if they want to train the first pattern (an image of a number zero for example) and they have n emitters, they will only switch on the first emitter the rest will stay off. This only makes it possible to create n different patterns, one for each transducer. An image of an architecture of the DAN model with just one hologram layer can be seen in Fig. 6.

Figure 6: Representation of architecture of the DAN Model with just one hologram layer

Then, in a different experiment, in order to create more patterns than input transducers, as inputs they switch on the first and second transducer at same time, then the first and third, ..., then second and third, etc... that is, all possible combinations of pairs emitters, which make it possible to create $\frac{n \cdot (n-1)}{2}$.

The disadvantages of this method is that they do not used all emitters at the same time, which this is, to use the whole phased array. In order to solve this, bellow there will be propose some architectures that try solve this problem.

3.3.2 One-Hot Layer Model

In order to train the inputs we are going to add before the phased array a one hot vector similar to the one in DAN but the length of this vector will be the number of patterns (P) we want to recreate, so the position of the one will represent the pattern chosen. Thus if we have P patterns we will fed the neural network with P one-hot vectors and train the model. A representation of the architecture of the model can be seen at Fig. 7.

Figure 7: Representation of the architecture with one fictional layer

Here the weights that connect the virtual part with physical part will be a matrix $P \times N^2$. Where for each column we will have N^2 amplitudes and phases to train for that specific pattern. As you can see, for the input the first subscript indicates the emitter and the second one indicates the pattern:

$$\begin{pmatrix} A_{11}e^{i\theta_{11}} & A_{12}e^{i\theta_{12}} & \dots & A_{1P}e^{i\theta_{1P}} \\ A_{21}e^{i\theta_{21}} & A_{22}e^{i\theta_{22}} & \dots & A_{2P}e^{i\theta_{2P}} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ A_{N^2 1}e^{i\theta_{N^2 1}} & A_{N^2 2}e^{i\theta_{N^2 2}} & \dots & A_{N^2 P}e^{i\theta_{N^2 P}} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ \vdots \\ 0 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} A_{11}e^{i\theta_{11}} \\ A_{21}e^{i\theta_{21}} \\ A_{31}e^{i\theta_{31}} \\ \vdots \\ A_{N^2 1}e^{i\theta_{N^2 1}} \end{pmatrix} \quad (8)$$

(N^2, P)
 $(P \times 1)$
 $(N^2, 1)$

The idea of this is to have a different set of amplitudes and phases for each pattern. Then this $N^2 \times 1$ vector specific for that pattern will link the real part joining to the equation (5).

This model has some advantages over DAN, this is that all transducer in the phase array participate in making all patterns. But also, has some disadvantages such as that although the phase shift in the holographic plate is trained to try to work for all patterns (because it is common to all patterns), the amplitudes and phases of the emitters of the phased array can not be consider as training, it will be more like an optimization because each pattern has his own set of parameters. This is a great disadvantage because the model would not be able to generalize to new patterns different to the ones the model has been training for. But still what can be done with this model is to try to fit the model with as many patterns as possible

and then try to obtain a generally well working holographic plate. This will be a plate that we know that works well on a vast majority of patterns and later on if the researcher wants to recreate a pattern for which the model has not been training for, he could just optimize his phased array according to that "well working" holographic plate.

But, although the capacity of generalizing is this type of problems is not very important, it will prevent to make a later optimization of the phased array according to that holographic plate. However, in order to being able to generalize, we need the model to be intelligent enough for that. This will try to be achieved with the new different architecture that will be presented bellow.

3.3.3 Encoder Decoder Diffractive Network

Figure 8: Representation of the architecture of the EDDN

The idea behind the Encoder Decoder Diffractive Network (EDDN) is to use the images itself as inputs for training the model. On this way, we don't need to use a one-hot layer with the number of patterns and this makes not necessary to have for each pattern a different set of weights. Thus, all the parameters are indeed share for all the images and can be trained rather than optimized. This permits the model to learn how to reconstruct images and being able to be used for prediction new patterns. So one way to achieve this is to make the inverse of the decoder (physical part) in the encoder (virtual part).

Even more, as the transfer matrices in the encoder (called T'_1 and T'_2 in the Virtual Part in Fig. 8) are not real, they don't necessarily need to be subjected to physics constraints, so T'_1 and T'_2 can be trainable parameters of the model.

Continuing with this idea as the encoder part is not real, it could be whatever we want, it is not necessary need to be symmetrical. It could be formed of fully connected linear layers or even as we are working with images as input, adding convolutional linear layers could be an

interesting idea.

One aspect to take into account when building the non real part is that the real part can not be totally invertible, the issue appears when we try to applied the the inverse of function f .

$$\begin{aligned}
 f : \mathbb{C} &\rightarrow \mathbb{R} & f^{-1} : \mathbb{R} &\rightarrow \mathbb{C} \\
 z = Ae^{i\theta} &\rightarrow f(z) = A & f(z) = A &\rightarrow f(z)^{-1} = Ae^{i\theta}
 \end{aligned} \tag{9}$$

As in the function f we go from being in the complex space that is a space of two dimensions (real part $Re(z)$ and imaginary part $Im(z)$) into a space of just one dimension, there is no issue because we have amplitudes and phases and we just care about the amplitudes, so we discard the phases, but when we want to do it on the other way, we know the amplitudes, but we don't know what the phases should be. To solve that, we can add arbitrary phases like all 0s or random phases or even been train it as a parameter of the model.

One of the problems of this model is that it requires a huge amount of parameters apart from the ones in the real part (that are by itself a lot too). In fact, for the non real part in order to connect the target distance with the holographic plate T'_2 is a matrix $S^2 \times M^2$, then the holographic plate has M^2 phase shifts and at the end to connect the holographic plate with the phased array a transfer matrix T'_1 of $M^2 \times N^2$ is needed, so this add $S^2 \cdot M^2 + M^2 + M^2 \cdot N^2$ which is equal to $M^2 \cdot (S^2 + N^2 + 1)$ more parameters just to compute the virtual part. On contrary, the one-hot layer model (previous model) just adds $P \cdot N^2$ new parameters, which is a considerable difference.

One way to reduce the number of parameters is, instead of having the transfer matrices T'_1 and T'_2 in the virtual part be trained, we will make them fixed and compute it using the same physical formula that we used for the transfer matrices in the physical part, but this will reduce a lot the power of the model. Even so, we will do it on this way, to being able to run the model due to computational power problems.

3.4 Simulation Set Up

In order to make a fair comparison between models, they will all be executed under the conditions, this means, same number of transducer in the phase array, same number of pixels in the holographic plate, same distance between the phased array, holographic plate and target distance, etc.

Both the phased array, the holographic plate as well as the surface where the pattern is located, will be squares of 16x16 cm each. As the whole idea of using holographic plates is for trying to achieve good quality patterns without the need of using many transducers, the number of transducer in the phased array will be small, this is 16 (a squared of 4x4), so $N = 4$. The holographic plate will have 64x64 individual points for which the wave travel and changes his phase, so $M = 64$ and finally the image pattern is discretized into 128x128 pixels or control points ($S = 128$).

The dataset of patterns for training the neural network will be extracted from the MNIST dataset [14]. This dataset consist of 60.000 training images and 10.000 test images of hand-written numbers from 0 to 9. This images are all 28×28 pixels each. For obtaining the patterns just one random image of each digit will be taken and there will be resize into 128×128 using the bilinear interpolation method [15]. The images selected can be shown at Fig. 9.

Figure 9: Dataset of the patterns

So the dataset will consist of just 10 images, when specified, we will use a larger dataset that also contains letters. This dataset will be extracted from the EMNIST dataset [16]. This, when needed, will add 26 more patterns, so the complete dataset will have 36 total patterns. This new images can be seen at Fig. 10.

Figure 10: Dataset of the patterns including Letters

The framework used to create and modify the neural networks will be TensorFlow [13].

The next discussion for the experimental set up must be: What should be the distances between the phased array and holographic plate? and to the target distance?

In order to select the perfect distances we are going to do a grid search of distances between 5 and 30 cm, taking steps of 5 cm for both distances (from Emitters (Phased Array) to the Holographic Plate and from the Holographic Plate to the Target). To measure the quality of the results we are going to report the negative value of the logarithmic of the mean squared error loss:

$$-\log(MSE) \tag{10}$$

This decision was taken because the loss was very close to 0, so there were a lot of zeros and it was difficult for the eye to see which values where smaller. Now, using equation 10 results are in logarithmic form and are more intuitive to see the differences (now, unlike for the mse, the more the better).

The grid search would be done for two models:

- DAN
- EDDN

The results can be seen at fig 11:

Figure 11: Grid Search of the log loss for different trying distances

As it can be see in the figure, the best distance for the Holographic Plate for both models is when the plate is very close to the Phased Array (5 cm). On the contrary, for the target distance it seems like around 20-30 cm from the Holographic Plate is the best distance. In this test the best distances are 5 cm and 20 cm for the DAN model and 5 cm and 25 cm for the EDDN method. As the EDDN method gives a higher loss, we will use 5 and 25 cm for

the final distance test for all the experiments.

A 3d representation of the final simulation set up be seen at Fig. 12.

Figure 12: 3d representation of the simulation set up

4 Results

4.1 Pure Array Optimization

The base method to compare against results, is usually pure array optimization. Pure array optimization consist of an optimization of just the phased array according to a target distance and just a pattern, which means to have no holographic plate and just optimize the phased array for an specific pattern. With just the phased array we can achieve good image resolution when the number of transducer is big enough [7].

For instance, by using 16×16 (512) transducers the simulations results have a very good resolution as it can be seen in Fig. 13.

ArrayAmpSlice 16x16 Log Loss: 5.7861

Figure 13: Mean Log Loss for the MNIST dataset using Pure Array Optimization with 16x16 transducers

Although, if instead of using 512 transducers that will involve a high cost, we used 16 transducers (4×4). The results are much worse. As it can be seen in Fig. 14.

ArrayAmpSlice 4x4 Log Loss: 2.3687

Figure 14: Mean Log Loss for the MNIST dataset using Pure Array Optimization with 4x4 transducers

As it can be seen in the images, no pattern can be distinguished, so in order to achieve a good resolution with a very few amount of transducers an holographic plate is needed. We will use both the model with 4×4 and the one with 16×16 results to compare with the different models discuss in this paper. The idea will be to try to outperform the classic pure array optimization with the same number of transducers 4×4 by adding the holographic plate and see if it can compete with the phased array that has 240 more emitters.

4.2 Diffracted Acoustic Network

Diffracted Acoustic Network (DAN) is the current best method for acoustic pattern generation using both a phased array and an holographic plate. Although in their paper they used more than one holographic plate, obtaining better results, here for our problem we will only use one holographic plate as the idea is to try to bring all this simulations to some real life experiments and we are forced to just use one holographic plate.

The simulations results obtain replicating the DAN method with 4×4 emitters are shown at Fig. 15.

Figure 15: Mean Log Loss for the MNIST dataset using DAN method with 4×4 transducers

As it can be seen in the image the DAN method is able to almost double the results of pure array optimization 4×4 , but still is 1 unit below this method when we use 240 more transducers. Even so, the patterns can be perfectly distinguish between them. One disadvantage of DAN is that we are forced to use just one transducer per pattern, so we loose a lot of power. Now, it is turn to see how it performs the models that use all transducers at the same time.

4.3 One-Hot Layer Model

The One-Hot Layer model, incorporates a one hot input vector of $(1 \times N.Patterns)$ dimension before the phased array layer, this makes that each pattern has its own pair of amplitudes and phases trained for make that specific pattern, resulting in a use of all the transducer at the same time. The acoustic pressure patterns generated with this models are shown at Fig. 22.

Figure 16: Mean Log Loss for the MNIST dataset using One Hot Layer Model with 4x4 transducers

As it can be seen, the model achieves about 0.5 more log loss units than the DAN model. This proves that the use of all the emitters at once performs better than just using one emitter per pattern. An example of how the one hot layer model use all the transducers at the same time can be seen at the Supplemental Information in Fig. 27.

4.4 Encoder Decoder Diffractive Network

Figure 17: Mean Log Loss for the MNIST dataset using the Encoder-Decoder Model with 4x4 transducers

As it can be appreciated on Fig. 17, the EDDN model has better loss than the previous models, but also has more parameters so the training is more expensive. Still they are not able to obtain better resolution than pure array optimization when uses 240 more emitters.

4.5 Comparison of all models

In order to make a comparison between all the models we will train the models with different number of patterns in the datasets. For this we will use both the MNIST and EMNIST

dataset explained in the experimental set up. We will compute the results for all the models explained and using both 4x4 and 16x16 transducers in the phased array. Results are shown in Table 1.

N. Patterns	ArrayAmp4 × 4	DAN4 × 4	OneHot4 × 4	EDDN4 × 4	ArrayAmp16 × 16	DAN16 × 16	OneHot16 × 16	EDDN16 × 16
1	2.575016	6.832472	5.647378	6.710172	5.498843	6.959398	5.962122	6.003410
2	2.869333	5.283944	6.367932	7.141631	5.761842	4.133021	6.590206	6.266028
3	2.796834	5.195768	6.377517	6.837344	5.622975	3.682206	6.825670	6.557240
4	2.742588	4.875667	6.338354	6.701730	5.604670	3.418805	6.452779	6.644028
5	2.831655	4.745792	6.331753	5.851975	5.685099	3.313510	6.611486	6.660971
6	2.823563	4.663406	5.999474	6.124025	5.652447	3.279502	6.448646	6.628277
7	2.790624	4.570724	5.831988	5.816370	5.695535	3.201134	6.281012	6.221437
8	2.783131	4.52635	5.506751	5.591366	5.469140	3.190218	6.288487	6.430957
9	2.770532	4.499083	5.320284	5.088617	5.405443	3.162776	6.502002	6.249623
10	2.755957	4.466246	5.067284	5.031923	5.434548	3.124454	6.128260	6.108799
11	2.745096	4.469185	4.908253	4.958215	5.402232	3.091897	6.195076	5.693188
12	2.729853	4.432047	4.855785	4.961229	5.377839	3.074676	6.088498	5.861040
13	2.709344	4.416377	4.546329	4.755369	5.395706	3.046923	6.257993	5.839122
14	2.717903	4.328341	4.461514	4.655101	5.367787	3.037177	6.132006	5.151098
15	2.728405	4.369721	4.447314	4.481391	5.350582	3.035635	5.965340	5.487315
16	2.724201	4.273734	4.364834	4.573129	5.393351	3.022809	6.064346	5.241032
17	2.717885	-	4.287466	4.426954	5.420611	3.006384	6.144506	5.191124
18	2.728515	-	4.231863	4.382349	5.406060	2.977415	5.875263	5.072109
19	2.740791	-	4.236287	4.392656	5.482078	2.972647	5.993216	5.125181
20	2.737294	-	4.140568	4.347224	5.327073	2.958785	6.020157	5.048000
21	2.718129	-	4.056518	4.096061	5.352228	2.930524	5.841179	4.944443
22	2.729428	-	4.151032	4.189607	5.234871	2.912600	5.911826	4.785452
23	2.746764	-	4.033381	4.220265	5.233908	2.910188	6.027016	4.796527
24	2.745650	-	4.002668	4.192032	5.183343	2.885713	6.070908	4.767665
25	2.734945	-	3.953484	4.184487	5.233879	2.864371	6.094308	4.862391
26	2.736192	-	3.999540	4.171921	5.144291	2.862345	5.849265	4.756981
27	2.748772	-	3.934195	4.145893	5.071000	2.850037	5.879921	4.802422
28	2.737918	-	3.911794	4.065598	5.074897	2.831346	6.081284	4.695708
29	2.732123	-	4.004441	3.906136	5.068943	2.827667	5.851877	4.453587
30	2.747672	-	3.884325	4.033484	5.090059	2.823598	5.811532	4.399318
31	2.744320	-	3.912122	4.012542	5.091320	2.805714	5.905230	4.520255
32	2.735354	-	3.895737	3.866368	5.111089	2.788945	5.701329	4.315735
33	2.741739	-	3.903576	3.832810	5.108865	2.734001	6.061327	4.523477
34	2.744239	-	3.775784	3.862657	5.117916	2.747728	6.029439	4.484844
35	2.753015	-	3.849150	3.825256	5.129606	2.763275	6.076796	4.361021
36	2.746948	-	3.770820	3.779227	5.152292	2.765591	6.126031	4.459760

Table 1: Table of the log losses of all the models depending on the number of patterns in the dataset

*Note that DAN4x4 can only performs until 16 patterns, because it only has 16 transducers. For more results, an example of the amplitude acoustic patterns generated by the OneHot4x4 with a dataset of 36 images can be seen in the supplemental information at Fig. 28.

A graph to understand better how the loss evolve as the number of patterns increase for all the different models can be seen a Fig. 18.

Figure 18: All losses for dataset with different number of patterns

Here are some conclusions of this comparison:

As we could have expected for the array amp slice the performance maintains stable along the number of patterns:

Figure 19: ArrayAmp Log Loss for different number of patterns dataset

That is because there is no training and each pattern is optimized individually which means that if we want to tune the phased array for 36 patterns we have to do 36 optimizations, thus means that if we want to do more and more patterns the computational time skyrockets. Also we can see that using a phased array of 16x16 transducers has better results than a phased array of 4x4 which make a lot sense.

Another interesting aspect which is logical is that the results for the models that uses an holographic plate get worse as we increase the number of patterns. That is because we are forcing the holographic plate to try to satisfy a greater number of patterns each time and this

results in an overall general decrease in the quality of the patterns. There will be a time when we could say that the plate has reached his limit, that is, there are too many patterns for that plate. Also we can see that with 16x16 emitters the workload of the holographic plate is reduce (thanks to having more emitters) and can take more patterns.

Figure 20: EDDN Log Loss for different number of patterns dataset

Despite of that, it seems that for the One-Hot Model with 16x16 emitters, the plate has not reached his 'limit' and still adding more patterns does not lead to a reduction in the overall general log loss, as it can be seen in Fig. 21:

Figure 21: One-Hot Model Log Loss for different number of patterns dataset

For more results, see the evolution of figure with number 1 shape, when training One Hot 4x4 with different amount of patterns in the dataset in the supplementary information at Fig. 29.

Surprisingly for DAN is backwards, the model with 4x4 performs better (at least up to the number of pattern it can take) than the model with 16x16 emitters:

Figure 22: DAN Log Loss for different number of patterns dataset

Maybe this can be explained because although DAN 16x16 has 256 transducers (240 more than DAN 4x4), in the way that DAN works, they are only switching 36 and the other 220 remains off for all the patterns. And so, for instance if we pick 10 patterns in DAN 4x4 this 10 transducers that will be on, they will be more separated and thus they reach more points in the holographic plate, however for DAN 16x16, those 10 transducer will be more together and they will share more points in holographic plate.

Finally, for an overall conclusion on Figure 18, we can see that the best model is the One Hot Layer model when having a phased array of 16×16 transducers, as it is above all models including pure array optimization, proving that under the same number of emitters having an holographic plate can add resolution to the acoustic pattern.

5 Conclusions and Future Work

In conclusion the use of an holographic plate can be beneficial to generate amplitude pattern specially when the number of transducers in the phased array is small. We have shown two different architectures that can used all emitters at the same time for generating different amplitude acoustic patterns for the same trained holographic plate.

As future work, new neural network architectures could be tested that focus especially on the virtual part of the neural network to try to make it more intelligent and capable of generalizing to new patterns which have not been trained on the network. One way to achieve this could be, for instance in the One-Hot model, to add densely connected layers between the One-Hot layer and the phased array or any other type of layers. Regarding in the Encoder Decoder Diffractive Network, since the input are images, it could be interesting to replace the encoder layers (that were symmetrical with the ones in the decoder part) with other more sophisticated layers such as convolutional layers or even try to use attention models, like transformers. An example can be seen at Fig. 23.

Figure 23: Example of a CNN Architecture for this problem

6 References

References

- [1] Oleg A Sapozhnikov et al. “Acoustic holography as a metrological tool for characterizing medical ultrasound sources and fields”. In: *The Journal of the Acoustical Society of America* 138.3 (2015), pp. 1515–1532.
- [2] Zhichao Ma et al. “Acoustic holographic cell patterning in a biocompatible hydrogel”. In: *Advanced Materials* 32.4 (2020), p. 1904181.
- [3] Zhixiong Gong and Michael Baudoin. “Particle assembly with synchronized acoustic tweezers”. In: *Physical Review Applied* 12.2 (2019), p. 024045.
- [4] Pieter Kruizinga et al. “Compressive 3D ultrasound imaging using a single sensor”. In: *Science advances* 3.12 (2017), e1701423.
- [5] Asier Marzo and Bruce W Drinkwater. “Holographic acoustic tweezers”. In: *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences* 116.1 (2019), pp. 84–89.
- [6] Weibai Li, Guoxing Lu, and Xiaodong Huang. “Acoustic hologram of the metasurface with phased arrays via optimality criteria”. In: *Mechanical Systems and Signal Processing* 180 (2022), p. 109420.
- [7] Tatsuki Fushimi, Kenta Yamamoto, and Yoichi Ochiai. “Acoustic hologram optimisation using automatic differentiation”. In: *Scientific reports* 11.1 (2021), p. 12678.
- [8] Boyi Li et al. “Acoustic Hologram Reconstruction With Unsupervised Neural Network”. In: *Frontiers in Materials* 9 (2022), p. 916527.
- [9] Qin Lin et al. “Multi-frequency acoustic hologram generation with a physics-enhanced deep neural network”. In: *Ultrasonics* 132 (2023), p. 106970.
- [10] Kai Melde et al. “Holograms for acoustics”. In: *Nature* 537.7621 (2016), pp. 518–522.

- [11] Athanasios G Athanassiadis et al. “Multi-plane Diffractive Acoustic Networks”. In: *IEEE Transactions on Ultrasonics, Ferroelectrics, and Frequency Control* (2023).
- [12] Marco AB Andrade et al. “Matrix method for acoustic levitation simulation”. In: *IEEE transactions on ultrasonics, ferroelectrics, and frequency control* 58.8 (2011), pp. 1674–1683.
- [13] Martín Abadi et al. *TensorFlow: Large-Scale Machine Learning on Heterogeneous Systems*. Software available from tensorflow.org. 2015. URL: <https://www.tensorflow.org/>.
- [14] Yann LeCun, Corinna Cortes, and CJ Burges. “MNIST handwritten digit database”. In: *ATT Labs [Online]*. Available: <http://yann.lecun.com/exdb/mnist> 2 (2010).
- [15] Wikipedia. *Bilinear interpolation — Wikipedia, The Free Encyclopedia*. <http://en.wikipedia.org/w/index.php?title=Bilinear%20interpolation&oldid=1170546721>. [Online; accessed 28-August-2023]. 2023.
- [16] Gregory Cohen et al. “EMNIST: Extending MNIST to handwritten letters”. In: *2017 international joint conference on neural networks (IJCNN)*. IEEE. 2017, pp. 2921–2926.

7 Supplemental Information

Summary of the models

DAN:

Layer (type)	Output Shape	Param #
input_1 (InputLayer)	[(None, 16)]	0
HolographicPlate (HoloPlate)	(None, 4096)	4096
OutputComplex (Lambda)	(None, 16384)	0
OutputAmp (Lambda)	(None, 16384)	0
OutputAmpNormalized (Lambda)	(None, 16384)	0
OutputAmpReshaped (Reshape)	(None, 128, 128)	0
Total params: 4,096		
Trainable params: 4,096		
Non-trainable params: 0		

Figure 24: Summary of DAN model

One-Hot:

Layer (type)	Output Shape	Param #
Inputs (InputLayer)	[(None, 10)]	0
emitters_plate_with_dense_weights (EmittersPlateWithDenseWeights)	(None, 16)	160
HolographicPlate (HoloPlate)	(None, 4096)	4096
OutputComplex (Lambda)	(None, 16384)	0
OutputAmp (Lambda)	(None, 16384)	0
OutputAmpNormalized (Lambda)	(None, 16384)	0
OutputAmpReshaped (Reshape)	(None, 128, 128)	0
=====		
Total params: 4,256		
Trainable params: 4,256		
Non-trainable params: 0		

Figure 25: Summary of OneHot model

Note that in this case emitters have 160 parameters because there was 16 transducers (4×4) and we train it for 10 patterns, so there are 16×10 parameters.

Encoder Decoder Diffractive Network:

Layer (type)	Output Shape	Param #
RawInputs (InputLayer)	[(None, 128, 128)]	0
Inputs (Flatten)	(None, 16384)	0
EncPlate1 (HoloPlate)	(None, 4096)	4096
Emitters (EmittersPlate)	(None, 16)	32
HolographicPlate (HoloPlate)	(None, 4096)	4096
OutputComplex (Lambda)	(None, 16384)	0
OutputAmp (Lambda)	(None, 16384)	0
OutputAmpNormalized (Lambda)	(None, 16384)	0
OutputAmpReshaped (Reshape)	(None, 128, 128)	0
=====		
Total params: 8,224		
Trainable params: 8,224		
Non-trainable params: 0		

Figure 26: Summary of EDDN model

Comparison of the use of the phased array between DAN 4x4 model and One Hot 4x4 model

Figure 27: Comparison of the use of the phased array between DAN 4x4 model and One Hot 4x4 model

Results of training with a dataset of 36 images

OneHot4x4 model when training with an dataset of 36 images. Log_loss: 3.8776

Figure 28: Results of training with a dataset of 36 images

Figure of number 1 when training One Hot 4x4 with different amount of patterns in the dataset

Figure 29: Evolution of number 1 when training with different dataset sizes